

SYNERGETIC EFFECT REVEALED BY SLIDING WEAR PERFORMANCE OF HYBRID NANOCOMPOSITES

M. Q. Zhang, M. Z. Rong, Q. B. Guo, G. L. Jia
Materials Science Institute, Zhongshan University
Guangzhou 510275, P. R. China
ceszmq@mail.sysu.edu.cn

SUMMARY

Addition of nano-SiO₂ and short carbon fiber into epoxy is able to generate positive synergetic effect in terms of tribological performance. The improved surface hardness (mainly resulting from carbon fiber), sheet-like wear debris reinforced by nano-SiO₂ that act as lubricant, and rapid formation of stable transfer film take the responsibility.

Keywords: Nanocomposites, carbon fiber, wear, friction, epoxy

INTRODUCTION

In this work, the hybrid effects of nano-SiO₂/short carbon fiber on the sliding wear performance of epoxy based composites were studied. The silica nanoparticles were pretreated by graft polymerization, an approach proved to be able to effectively improve tribological properties of inorganic nanoparticles/epoxy composites [1]. Maleic anhydride (MA) and styrene (St) were selected as the monomers of the copolymer grafted onto nano-SiO₂, respectively. The former can react with epoxy so as to chemically connect the grafted nanoparticles with the composites matrix, while the appearance of the latter reduces the amount of reactive groups (i.e. anhydride) on the grafting chains to provide the interphase with certain flexibility. It is expected an optimum recipe for producing hybrid composites that makes full use of the advantages of nano-SiO₂ and carbon fiber can be acquired at relatively lower filler content.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

Bisphenol-A epoxy resin (type E-51) was supplied by Guangzhou Dongfeng Chemical Co., China. The curing agent, 4,4-diamino-diphenylsulfone (DDS), was purchased from the National Medicine Co. of Shanghai, China. Nano-SiO₂ (Aerosil 200) was supplied by Degussa Co., Germany, with an average size of 12 nm and a specific surface area of 200m²/g. Silane coupling agent, γ -methacryloxypropyl trimethoxy silane (trade name: KH570), was provided by Lianing Gaizhou Chemical Industry Co., China. Pitch-based carbon fibers (CF) with a diameter of 7 μ m and a length of 1 mm were offered by Shanghai Special Fiber Co., China. Maleic anhydride (MA), styrene (St) and benzoyl peroxide (BPO) were supplied by Guangzhou Chemical Agent Factory, China.

Surface treatment of nano-SiO₂ and composites preparation

To provide the nano-SiO₂ with sufficient reactivity for the subsequent graft polymerization, double bonds have to be introduced onto the particles surface in advance by silane pretreatment. The details have been described in detail elsewhere [2]. The silane coupling agent pretreated nano-SiO₂ (the weight ratio of the coupling agent to the nanoparticles was 6.84 wt.%) was dried in vacuum at 50°C for 24h. After that, graft copolymerization of St and MA (SMA) onto the nanoparticles was conducted as follows. 2.0g dried silane pretreated nano-SiO₂ and 80ml toluene were charged into a three-neck flask fitted with a stirrer. Having been ultrasonically agitated for 30min, the mixture was placed into oil bath equipped with a condenser under flowing of dry nitrogen. When the temperature reached 80°C, the initiator (0.0484g BPO in 10ml toluene) was added. After 30 min, the mixed monomers (2.08g St and 0.245g MA in 10ml toluene) were filled into the flask in one batch. The reaction took 5h and then the product was filtered, washed, and extracted with xylene for 8h to remove the homopolymerized PS and with acetone for 24h to get rid of homopolymer of polystyrene-maleic anhydride. The content of the copolymer grafted onto the nano-SiO₂ (denoted by SiO₂-g-SMA) was detected by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA, Netzsch 209 thermogravimetric analyzer). The grafted nanoparticles with a percent grafting of 17.2% was selected for filling epoxy composites.

The epoxy composites were prepared by firstly mixing the pre-weighted quantities of epoxy and nano-SiO₂ (in original or grafted form) at 80°C for 3h and ultrasonically stirred for 1h. Afterwards, the compounds were heated to 130°C and blended with the curing agent DDS. After stirring for 15min, the pre-cured nano-SiO₂/epoxy compounds were mixed with short carbon fiber at 100°C under stirring for 10min. Then, the composites were transferred to a leaky mold, heated to 140°C in vacuum for 90min to remove air bubbles, and pressed at the same temperature for 30min. At last, the specimen plate of 100×80×6mm³ was ready for testing after post-curing at 180°C for 2h and 200°C for 2h. For the convenience of discussion, the total filler contents in all the specimens were fixed at 10wt.%.

Characterization

An Equinox 55 Fourier transformation infrared (FTIR) spectrometer was used to characterize structural changes in the materials. Dispersion status of the nanoparticles before and after the graft treatment in acetone (3mg sample in 10ml acetone) was monitored by dynamic light scattering with a vertically polarized He-Ne laser (Brooken Haven BI-200SM goniometer) at 25°C and a fixed scattering angle of 90°.

Unlubricated sliding wear tests were carried out on a block-on-ring apparatus (M-200) under a constant velocity of 0.42m/s and a constant pressure of 3MPa. The carbon steel ring (0.42~0.45 wt.% C, 0.17~0.37 wt.% Si and 0.5~0.8 wt.% Mn, HRC 50) had a diameter of 40mm, and an average initial surface roughness was about 0.2μm. The specimens for wear tests were machined with a geometry of 6×10×16mm³, resulting in an apparent contact area of about 6mm×10mm. The testing period was set at 3h. After each wear test, the specimen's weight loss was weighed, so that the specific wear rate can be estimated. Besides, the worn surfaces of the specimens were observed with a

Quanta 400F scanning electron microscope (SEM), and the transfer film formed on the steel rings was investigated with SEM and scanning probe microscope (P47H SPM), respectively. Microhardness of the materials was determined by a Shimadzu DUH-W201S dynamic microhardness tester with an indentation mode at a load of 1.5N and holding time of 60s. For each specimen 15 points were measured.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Since the present work incorporated reactive nano-SiO₂ into the composites, the chemical structural variation of the nanoparticles before and after the graft treatment should be known at the beginning. Fig.1(a) gives the FTIR spectra of the particles. On the spectrum of the silane pre-treated nano-SiO₂, appearance of the peak at 1712cm⁻¹ is indicative of carbonyl groups from the coupling agent. As for the spectrum of SiO₂-g-SMA, the adsorptions at 1783 and 1858cm⁻¹ are attributed to the stretching mode of carbonyl groups of the cyclic anhydride, while the peaks at 1455 and 1495cm⁻¹ are due to the stretching of phenyl framework. The findings suggest that both maleic anhydride and styrene have been attached to the nano-SiO₂ as expected. Under the present conditions, a structure of alternating copolymer of St and MA should be obtained prior to the exhaustion of MA monomer [3]. Finally, only PS chain fragment is formed.

Fig.1

FTIR spectra of (a) nano-SiO₂ and its treated versions, and (b) epoxy, SiO₂-g-SMA, and the cured blends of epoxy and SiO₂-g-SMA.

To confirm whether the grafted nanoparticles can react with epoxy, a model mixture of SiO₂-g-SMA and epoxy (weight content of SiO₂-g-SMA in epoxy: 10%) excluding any curing agent was fabricated and thermally treated following the same curing sequence as that applied for the composites mentioned in the Experimental part. Then, the blend was extracted with acetone for 50h. Visual inspection told that the mixture was indeed consolidated. Besides, by comparing the infrared spectra in Fig.1(b), one can see that the characteristic peaks of MA at 1783 and 1858cm⁻¹ nearly disappear on the spectrum of the cured SiO₂-g-SMA/epoxy mixture. Meanwhile, a new peak at 1736cm⁻¹ is perceivable because of disintegration of the cyclic anhydride and formation of carbonyl groups. It can thus be concluded that the grafting chain of SMA is able to react with epoxy during the curing process, which would certainly enhance the filler/matrix adhesion in the composites.

Like other fibrous materials, either continuous or discontinuous carbon fibers are able to reduce wear rate and friction coefficient of polymers mainly due to their remarkable load carrying capability [4]. Similarly, nano-SiO₂ particles can also improve tribological performance of epoxy by changing the wear mechanism from severe abrasive wear to mild sliding wear [5]. When these two types of additives are incorporated into the composites, a desirable synergetic effect appears (Fig.2). It is interesting to find that the composites with 4wt.% nano-SiO₂ and 6wt.% carbon fiber have the lowest specific wear rate, \dot{w}_s , and friction coefficient, μ . Compared to the case of unfilled epoxy ($\dot{w}_s=3.1 \times 10^{-4} \text{mm}^3/\text{Nm}$, $\mu=0.55$), the improvement is significant. Although nano-silica is less effective in reducing wear rate and friction coefficient than short carbon fiber, a combination of nano-silica and short carbon fiber can get much better outcomes. Moreover, the grafted nano-SiO₂ is superior to the untreated version, reflecting the importance of filler/matrix interfacial bonding.

Fig.2 (a) Specific wear rate, \dot{w}_s , and (b) friction coefficient, μ , of epoxy based nanocomposites. For reference, the specific wear rate and friction coefficient of unfilled epoxy are listed as follows: $3.1 \times 10^{-4} \text{mm}^3/\text{Nm}$ and 0.55, respectively. The total filler contents in all the specimens are fixed at 10wt.%.

In general, surface hardness is one of the most important factors that govern materials' wear resistance. Harder surface would have higher wear resistance. To understand the synergetic effect revealed in Fig.2, microhardness of the specimens was measured (Fig.3). Carbon fiber reinforced epoxy can be considered as "body" phases dispersed into a "soft" phase [6], which increases hardness and creep resistance of the composites and reduces wear rate and friction coefficient. However, the addition of nano-SiO₂ decreases the hardness of carbon fiber/epoxy composites. Although microhardness of the composites with 4wt.% nano-SiO₂ and 6wt.% carbon fiber are almost the highest among those containing nano-silica, it is still lower than the composites with 10wt.% carbon fiber. That is, the dependence of microhardness on the composites' components weight ratios does not exactly agree with the trends in Fig.2. Other factors in addition to the enhancement of hardness should account for the improved friction and wear properties of the composites.

Fig.3 Microhardness of epoxy based nanocomposites. The total filler contents in all the specimens are fixed at 10wt.%.

Fig.4 shows SEM micrographs of the worn surface of the specimens. For neat epoxy (Fig.4(a)), fatigue wear is the main mechanism responsible for material loss in the form of thin sheets. When untreated nano-SiO₂ is incorporated, the worn morphology of the composites (Fig.4(b)) is similar to that of the unfilled version (Fig.4(a)). It means that the particles/matrix interaction is not strong enough to resist the repeated shear loading during wear test. Crack initiation, growth and coalescence take place in the sub-layer of the worn surface. Nevertheless, the worn surface of grafted nano-SiO₂/epoxy composites becomes less coarse (Fig.4(c)). Splinted wear debris is found in some regions, which helps to protect the bulk material from severe wear. Evidently, the chemical bonding between silica nanoparticles and the matrix resin increases integrity of the composites. As for the composites with short carbon fiber, fiber thinning, breakage and peeling off are the dominant wear modes (Fig.4(d)) [7], implying that a major share of normal load was supported by the fibers [8]. The detached fiber debris could act as third body abrasive [9], leading to higher wear rate and friction coefficient. However, it is worth noting that number of the cavities left by detachment of carbon fiber is reduced after the incorporation of nano-SiO₂ (Fig.4(e)). This is particularly true for the system containing the treated nanoparticles (Fig.4(f)), in which large scale material loss characterized by filler pull-out is nearly absent.

Fig.4(a)

Fig.4(b)

Fig.4(c)

Fig.4(d)

Fig.4(e)

Fig.4(f)

Fig.4 SEM micrographs of the worn surface of (a) unfilled epoxy, (b) SiO₂/EP (SiO₂: 10wt.%), (c) SiO₂-g-SMA/EP (SiO₂: 10wt.%), and (d) CF/EP (CF: 10wt.%), (e) SiO₂/CF/EP (SiO₂/CF: 4/6(wt/wt)), (f) SiO₂-g-SMA/CF/EP (SiO₂/CF: 4/6(wt/wt)). The arrows indicate the sliding direction.

To further understand the wear mechanism, the surface of the counterpart steel rings that had rubbed against the composites specimens was also observed by SEM (Fig.5). Fig.5(a) and Fig.5(b) indicate that transfer films were discontinuously developed on the steel counterface after sliding on the grafted nano-SiO₂/epoxy and carbon fiber/epoxy composites, respectively. For the counterface rubbing against the hybrid composites, uniform transfer films were generated, covering the entire region of interests (Fig.5(c) and Fig.5(d)). The formation of transfer film for epoxy composites/steel pairs has long been reported [10]. It certainly favors the reduction in wear rate and friction coefficient.

The results in Fig.4 and Fig.5 well coincide with the data in Fig.2. It is believed that for the hybrid composites carbon fibers take the responsibility of load bearing while the tiny sheet-like wear debris reinforced by nano-SiO₂ act as polishing agent [11]. Interfacial abrasion is greatly weakened owing to the lack of grit-like wear particles. Meantime, compact transfer films are built up, and the bonding between the transfer film and the counterface is improved by the nanoparticles [1]. These in turn lower the frictional temperature to a much greater extent. Wear of the composites becomes rather mild as a result.

Recently, Lee and co-workers conducted computer simulations and showed that adding nanoparticles to polymers yielded materials in which the particles became localized at nanoscale cracks and effectively form "patches" to repair the damaged regions [12]. Their results support our consideration of the role of the nanoparticles.

Fig.5(a)

Fig.5(b)

Fig.5(c)

Fig.5(d)

Fig.5 SEM micrographs of the steel counterpart surface that had rubbed against (a) SiO₂-g-SMA/EP (SiO₂: 10wt.%), (b) CF/EP (CF: 10wt.%), (c) SiO₂/CF/EP (SiO₂/CF:

4/6(wt/wt)), and (d) SiO₂-g-SMA/CF/EP (SiO₂/CF: 4/6(wt/wt)). The arrows indicate the sliding direction.

Typical time dependences of friction coefficient of the materials are recorded in Fig.6. During the entire period of testing, friction coefficients of both unfilled epoxy and untreated nano-SiO₂ reinforced epoxy remain at a high level. With respect to the rest composites, a drop in friction coefficient is observed with increasing time, which corresponds to transfer film formation. By comparing Fig.2 and Fig.6, it is inferred that the specific wear rate is greatly dependent on the formation rate of transfer film. In other words, the faster the transfer film is formed, the lower the wear rate. In the case of CF/EP composites (CF = 10wt.%), for example, the transfer film starts to be formed at about 17min of the test, while 30min is required for SiO₂-g-SMA/EP composites (SiO₂ = 10wt.%). Accordingly, the specific wear rate of CF/EP is about 5 times lower than that of SiO₂-g-SMA/EP. For the hybrid composites reinforced by both nano-silica and carbon fiber, the time taken for forming transfer film is only about 10min, which corresponds to the lowest wear rate as convinced by Fig.2.

Fig.6 Time dependences of friction coefficient of epoxy and its nanocomposites.

CONCLUSIONS

The addition of nano-SiO₂ and short carbon fiber into epoxy is able to generate positive synergetic effect in terms of tribological performance. A composite containing 4wt.% nano-SiO₂ and 6wt.% short carbon fiber exhibits significantly lower wear rate and friction coefficient than those filled with individual nano-SiO₂ and short carbon fiber, respectively.

Surface graft treatment of nano-SiO₂ by introducing SMA copolymer helps to strengthen interfacial interaction between the nanoparticles and matrix resin. It further gives play to the nanoparticles, whether the grafted nanoparticles are added alone or together with carbon fiber into epoxy.

The synergetic effect observed in the hybrid composites is attributed to the improved surface hardness (mainly resulting from carbon fiber), sheet-like wear debris reinforced by nano-SiO₂ that act as lubricant, and rapid formation of uniform and stable transfer film.

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